

Thermodynamic studies of adduct formation reactions between organotin(IV)dichlorides and Ni^{II} macrocycles

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Abstract : This article presents σ -acceptor strength for the diorganotin(IV)dichlorides : dimethyltin dichloride, diphenyltin dichloride and dibutyltin dichloride as Lewis acids toward some macrocyclic nickel(II) complexes. Thermodynamic of the adducts formation of the tin(IV)dichlorides with Ni(II)tetraaza Schiff base complexes such as : [Ni(Me₄-Bzo₂[14]-tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₄-4-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₄-4-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] and [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-4-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-4-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] that Me₄-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄ denotes : (5,7,12,14-tetramethyldibenzo[b,i][1,4,8,11]tetraazacyclo-tetradecine), was studied in acetonitrile by means of UV-Vis spectrophotometric analysis. The thermodynamic parameters and the formation constant values show the acidity trend for diorganotin(IV)dichlorides as follow : Ph₂SnCl₂ > Me₂SnCl₂ > Bu₂SnCl₂. Adducts have been synthesized and fully characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹¹⁹Sn NMR, IR, UV-Vis spectra and elemental microanalysis (C.H.N) methods. The trend of the adduct formation of the nickel complexes with a given tin acceptor decrease as follow : [Ni(Me₄-4-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] > [Ni(Me₄-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] > [Ni(Me₄-4-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] > [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-4-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] > [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] > [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-4-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)].

Keywords : Diorganotin(IV)dichlorides, thermodynamic, tetraaza Schiff base, nickel(II) complex.

Introduction

The interest in tetradentate Schiff base complexes of the first row transition metals is to a significant extent based on the fact that they can serve as models for some biomolecules¹⁻³. While Schiff bases with N₂O₂ coordination sphere have been widely studied, it should be mentioned that MN₄ tetra-dentate Schiff base complexes were investigated in less details. The ability of salicylaldimine complexes to act as effective donor ligands to tin(IV)halides is well documented⁴⁻⁷. In contrast to the extensive literatures on the transition quadri-dentate Schiff base metal complexes, rather little is known about the molecular interaction of these complexes as neutral donors with tin Lewis acids as acceptors. Few investigations on the molecular interaction between donor-acceptor systems have been done^{8,9}. The crystal structures of SnPh₃Cl·[Ni(3-MeO-salpn)]·H₂O [H₂-3-MeO-salpn = N,N'-bis(3-methoxysalicylidene)propane-1,3-diamine] reveal that in adduct the water molecule coordinated to tin engaged in hydrogen bonding interactions with the Schiff base oxygen atoms¹⁰.

Several studies have been done on the molecular interaction between acceptor-donor systems, specially the molecular structure of transition metal Schiff base complexes as ligands for tin chemistry. Previous studies have been shown that transition metal Schiff base complexes especially Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II} salicylaldimines are effective neutral donor ligands for tin(IV)halides, pseudo halides and tin(II)halides⁶⁻¹¹.

According to this background, in this paper we investigated the thermodynamic of Lewis acid-base interactions between nickel(II) symmetric and asymmetric macrocycle containing dianionic tetraazaannulene, as neutral donor ligands and diorganotin(IV)dichloride as Lewis acid.

The results of this work are important especially from the point of view that organotin complexes have been demonstrated to exhibit relatively high antitumour activity^{12,13}. On the other hand metal macrocycle complexes were used as biomolecule models such as vitamin B₁₂. One reason that such systems have aroused interest is their ability to model biological phenomena, such as bind-

ing of molecules to iron in various haem systems. It is understandable then why special attention has been paid to synthetic macrocycles which resemble but also differ from the naturally occurring porphyrins. Transition metal complexes derived from ligands of the type that we studied have been prepared and studied by a number of investigators with most of the studies confine to nickel(II) complexes. These complexes have a number of features in common with porphyrin and phthalocyanine ligands, but also have significant differences¹⁴. It is worth to note that till now no study has been done on the thermodynamics of adduct formation between Ni^{II} macrocycle complexes and diorganotin(IV)dichlorides.

This paper describe synthesis of some Ni^{II} macrocycle complexes and thermodynamic studies of novel 2 : 1 adduct formation of diorganotin(IV)dichlorides such as Me₂SnCl₂, Bu₂SnCl₂ and Ph₂SnCl₂ as Lewis acids with Ni^{II} macrocycle complexes such as : [Ni(Me₄-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₄-4-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₄-4-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] and [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-4-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-4-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] (Fig. 1) as donors in acetonitrile solvent. By comparing values of log *K_f* we investigated the electronic and steric effect of substituents on both Ni^{II} macrocycle complexes and diorganotin(IV)dichlorides on the equilib-

Fig. 1. The structure of nickel(II)macrocycle complexes. R = H, Me, Cl.

rium constants of adduct formation. Also with a suitable selection of acceptor species and solvent, we successfully synthesized the products; these synthesized adducts were confirmed by using ¹H NMR, ¹¹⁹Sn NMR, IR, UV-Vis spectra and elemental microanalysis (C.H.N) methods.

Experimental

Reagents :

All chemicals were used as obtained from Merck, Fluka or Acros. Anal. Grade solvent from Merck was used without further purification.

Instruments :

Light-absorption measurements in the visible region were made with a Perkin-Elmer-UV-Vis spectrophotometer-Lambda 2, equipped with a Lauda-ecoline-RE thermostat. FT-IR spectra were run on a Shimadzu FTIR-8300 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance DPX-250 spectrometer in DMSO-*d*₆, CDCl₃ solvent using TMS as an internal standard. ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance DPX-400 spectrometer in DMSO-*d*₆ solvent. Elemental micro-analyses (C.H.N.) were obtained using a Thermo Finnigan-CHNSO Analyzer.

Synthesis of nickel(II) macrocycle complexes :

The nickel(II) complexes used in this study were prepared according to previously published methods with a small modification^{15,16}.

Synthesis of adducts of diorganotin(IV)dichloride with Ni(II)macrocycle complexes :

The adduct complexes were prepared using a method described in the literature by Cunningham *et al.*⁶⁻¹¹. Typically, 0.01 mol of the tin Lewis acid was added to 0.02 mol of the metal complex in 100 ml of acetonitrile. The mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature and the crystals of adduct complex filtered off and dried under the vacuum.

Equilibrium measurements :

The adduct complexes were obtained from the reaction of acceptors with donors, according to eq. (1) :

mac = (Me₄-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄), (Me₄-CH₃Bzo₂[14]-

tetraeneN₄), (Me₄-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄), (Me₂Ph₂-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄), (Me₂Ph₂-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄), (Me₂Ph₂-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄), R = Me, Bu, Ph.

A solution from each complex with concentration about 10⁻⁵ M was prepared. In a typical measurement, 2.5 ml of this solution was transferred into the thermostated cell compartment of the UV-Visible instrument, which was kept at constant temperature (runs from 10–40 ± 0.1 °C) by circulating water and was titrated by excess concentration of the diorganotin(IV)dichloride (20–200 folds). The titration was performed by adding aliquots of the diorganotin(IV)dichloride with a Hamilton µL syringe to the complex. The absorption measurements were carried out at various wavelengths where the difference in absorption was the maximum after the equilibrium was assessed. The formed adduct shows absorption different from the donor, while the acceptors show no absorption at those wavelengths. As an example, the variation of the electronic spectra for [Ni(Me₄-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], titrated with Bu₂SnCl₂ at 20 °C in CH₃CN is shown in Fig. 2. The isosbestic points show that there is only one reaction in equilibrium. The same procedure was followed for other systems. The formation constants of the adduct formation were calculated in the selected range of spectra by using the well-known SQUAD program. SQUAD is a program with the capability of refining the stability constants of a general complex M_mM_lH_kL_nL_q, where *m*, *l*, *k*, *n*, *q* > 0 and *k* is positive for protons, negative for hy-

droxide ions or zero, employing a non-linear least-squares approach. The data fed to SQUAD are absorption spectra, chemical composition (total concentrations of M, M', L, L' and pH) and a chemical model to describe the system. The residual sum (*U*) is calculated from the following equation :

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^{NW} (A_{i,k}^{\text{calc.}} - A_{i,k}^{\text{obs}})^2$$

where the *A*_{*i,k*} is the absorbance value of the *i*-th solution at the *k*-th wavelength, given a total of *I* solutions and a grand total of *NW* wavelength¹⁷.

Results and discussion

Spectral characterization :

Electronic spectra :

Absorption spectra of the nickel complexes were examined over the 300–800 nm range, and the results are summarized in Table 1. The complexes exhibit one intense absorption band in the visible region. This band is unique to the metal complexes and has energy maxima ranging from 580 to 600 nm. Several intense absorptions are observed in the near-UV regions of the spectrum. The higher energy bands fall in the region characteristic of the free base ligand and apparently intraligand electronic transitions. Upon the interaction of nickel macrocycle complexes with diorganotin(IV)dichlorides, the original peaks of nickel complexes changed and new peaks

Fig. 2. The absorption spectra of [Ni(Me₄-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], with Bu₂SnCl₂ at 20 °C in CH₃CN with the isosbestic points.

Table 1. UV-Vis bands λ_{\max} (CH₃CN/nm) of the nickel macrocycle complexes and their adducts with diorganotin dichlorides

Complex	λ (ϵ (M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹))
[Ni(Me ₄ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)]	329 (5200), 390 (27250), 582 (3750)
[Ni(Me ₄ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] adduct	392, 422 (sh), 618
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)]	332 (sh), 390 (25640), 582 (4000)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] adduct	328, 394, 615
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)]	335 (sh), 393 (26540), 580 (4100)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] adduct	398, 590
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)]	337 (4300), 396 (28100), 439 (sh), 598 (2450)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] adduct	402, 434 (sh), 628
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)]	396 (9800), 594 (1490)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] adduct	401, 654
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)]	340 (sh), 400 (8790), 444 (sh), 600 (1200)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] adduct	407, 439 (sh), 622

appeared (Fig. 2).

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra data of nickel complexes and adducts are collected in Table 2. In the ¹H NMR spectra of complexes (Fig. 3) the CH, CH₃ protons of the ligand appear as a sharp singlet, and the protons of the aromatic rings appear as a multiplet in the region 6.23–7.94 ppm. The formation of adducts with diorganotin dichlorides are identified by appearance of Me₂SnCl₂ index peaks in the region of δ 1.00–1.52 ppm, and for Bu₂SnCl₂ in δ 0.91–2.60 ppm and the peaks related to Ph₂SnCl₂ are observed in aromatic region.

Adduct formation causes low field shifts of the protons, with compare to parent complexes.

¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

Holeček and coworkers studies result show that in the di- and tri-organotin the ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra can be used as an indicator of the coordination number of the tin atom. In the range of +200 to –60, –90 to –190, –210 to –400, –440 to –540 ppm, the coordination number of the tin are four, five, six and seven^{18–21}. The adduct complexes of the presents investigation exhibit the ¹¹⁹Sn spectra in the range –333.45 to –418.54 ppm (see for example Fig. 4), suggesting that the tin atoms are six-coordinate (Table 3).

IR spectra :

The weak bands of IR spectra between (2850–3076) cm⁻¹ are related to (C-H) modes of vibrations. The vibra-

Table 2. ¹H NMR characterization of the nickel macrocycle complexes and their adducts with diorganotin dichlorides

Complex	R ₂ SnCl ₂	Ar-H	C-H	CH ₃
1		6.23–6.71	4.81	2.08
1a	1.05–1.21	6.32–6.85	5.12	2.22
1b	0.91–2.12	6.27–6.82	5.14	2.12
1c		6.32–7.72	5.22	2.34
2		6.39–6.58	4.87	2.09, 2.13
2a	1.08–1.11	7.19–7.58	5.38	2.16, 2.23
2b	0.95–2.15	7.39–7.28	5.37	2.15, 2.23
2c		7.26–7.98	5.55	2.18, 2.25
3		6.47–6.64	4.91	2.12
3a	1.02–1.22	7.03–7.64	5.31	2.71
3b	0.93–2.12	7.47–7.89	5.43	2.98
3c		7.19–7.94	5.38	3.58
4		6.64–7.31	5.01	2.20
4a	1.12–1.52	7.24–7.71	6.01	3.13
4b	1.00–2.38	7.59–8.31	6.22	3.33
4c		7.84–8.55	6.18	3.20
5		6.90–7.90	4.95	2.17, 2.39
5a	1.25–1.52	7.77–8.35	5.75	2.58, 3.05
5b	1.08–2.58	7.89–8.60	5.37	2.74, 3.37
5c		8.02–8.87	6.01	2.83, 3.14
6		7.24–7.53	5.05	2.31
6a	1.00–1.34	7.44–8.63	6.02	3.11
6b	1.10–2.60	7.71–8.53	6.33	3.42
6c		7.23–8.78	6.29	3.12

tions of the azomethine groups (C=N) are observed at (1509–1604) cm⁻¹ range. The stronger bands in the (1384–

Fig. 3. ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)]$ in CDCl_3 .

Fig. 4. ^{119}Sn NMR spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)]_2\cdot\text{Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$.

Table 3. ^{119}Sn NMR characterization of some nickel adducts with diorganotin dichlorides

Complex	^{119}Sn
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-354.34
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-4-CH}_3\text{Bzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-337.43
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-4-ClBzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-336.54
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-4-ClBzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-418.54
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-388.65
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-333.45
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-4-CH}_3\text{Bzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-367.12
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-4-ClBzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-379.33
$[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-4-ClBzo}_2[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)_2\cdot\text{Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$	-411.67

1475) cm^{-1} are due to the skeleton stretching vibration of C=C of the benzene ring. The bands at about 414–456 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the (Ni-N) group vibrations. These bands are characteristic of the complexes and were not found in the free ligand spectra. The results show that, by formation of adducts, the C=N vibrations shifted toward higher frequencies. The ring skeletal vibrations (C=C) were weakly affected by complexation. In IR spectra of the adducts, vibration band in (3544–3621) cm^{-1} is assigned to (O-H) stretching due to H_2O , that we suggest to exist in the adduct complexes (Table 4).

Elemental microanalysis :

Elemental analysis of the products has good agreement with adducts of composition 2 : 1 for Ni(mac) : R_2SnCl_2 and also with two H_2O molecules (Table 5).

The formation constants and the thermodynamic parameter calculations :

The thermodynamic parameters are useful tools for studying these interactions and understanding the relative stability of adducts. The formation constants were determined at several temperatures by analyzing the concentration and temperatures dependence of UV-Vis absorptions by the SQUAD program (Table 6). These absorptions were analyzed by using the following mole ratios of the acids to base as models of interaction between R_2SnCl_2 and Ni(mac) : (1) formation of the 1 : 1 adduct, (2) formation of the 1 : 2 adduct, (3) simultaneous formation of the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 adducts. The fit of the model to the experimental data, 15 points, is measured by the sum of the squares of the deviations of the experimental points from the point calculated by the model. For the proposed

Table 4. IR bands (cm^{-1}) characterization of the nickel macrocycle complexes and their adducts with diorganotin dichloride

Complex	$\nu_{\text{O-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=C}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$
1		2963, 2855	1543	1462, 1398	420
1a	3554	2981, 2885	1559	1466, 1385	433
1b	3559	2972, 2993	1547	1468, 1393	445
1c	3553	2978, 2877	1563	1464, 1400	442
2		3026, 2918	1545	1461, 1392	439
2a	3564	3032, 2938	1560	1463, 1395	450
2b	3562	3042, 2960	1551	1464, 1384	444
2c	3576	3054, 2971	1550	1443, 1392	442
3		2965, 2924	1544	1461, 1392	419
3a	3564	2980, 2933	1557	1475, 1398	422
3b	3554	2978, 2943	1586	1465, 1392	435
3c	3579	2977, 2956	1547	1463, 1390	447
4		2922, 2853	1570	1459, 1392	418
4a	3555	2933, 2875	1604	1461, 1403	428
4b	3601	2937, 2882	1584	1466, 1407	435
4c	3621	2942, 2863	1596	1474, 1410	427
5		3056, 3023	1516	1461, 1392	420
5a	3544	3076, 3038	1527	1451, 1387	422
5b	3557	3071, 3033	1530	1463, 1388	456
5c	3579	3071, 3045	1523	1473, 1392	437
6		2920, 2853	1509	1450, 1400	414
6a	3553	2936, 2857	1519	1464, 1406	423
6b	3567	2942, 2861	1532	1457, 1397	438
6c	3579	2937, 2862	1511	1450, 1386	415

models, the formation of the 1 : 2 adducts of acid to base has the best fitting and the produced error sum of squares was between 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} . In a parallel method, by using Ketelaar's eq. (3), the formation constants of the various nickel(II)macrocycle (base) with different diorganotin dichloride (acid) were calculated²² :

$$C_A^0 C_D^0 / (A - A_A^0 - A_D^0) = 1 / (\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D) \cdot [1/K + (C_A^0 + C_D^0)] \quad (3)$$

where C_A^0 and C_D^0 are the initial concentrations (M) of the acceptor and the donor, respectively; A is the optical density of the solution including the acceptor and the donor, A_A^0 and A_D^0 are the optical densities of the pure acceptor and the pure donor in the solution of concentration C_A^0 and C_D^0 ; ϵ_C , ϵ_A and ϵ_D are the molar extinction coefficients ($M^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) of the complex, the acceptor and the donor, respectively. K is the formation constant of

Table 5. Elemental analysis of complexes and adducts

Complex	C	H	N
[Ni(Me ₄ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] (1)	65.81 (65.87)	5.51 (5.53)	13.94 (13.97)
[Ni(Me ₄ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (1a)	52.26 (52.22)	5.16 (5.14)	10.57 (10.59)
[Ni(Me ₄ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Bu ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (1b)	54.63 (54.68)	5.82 (5.82)	9.84 (9.81)
[Ni(Me ₄ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (1c)	58.19 (58.11)	5.56 (5.53)	9.06 (9.03)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] (2)	67.12 (67.16)	6.12 (6.11)	13.07 (13.05)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (2a)	53.86 (53.81)	5.79 (5.78)	10.09 (10.04)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Bu ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (2b)	56.33 (56.23)	6.11 (6.07)	9.40 (9.37)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (2c)	58.25 (58.11)	5.55 (5.53)	9.06 (9.03)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] (3)	56.34 (56.22)	4.29 (4.29)	12.00 (11.92)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (3a)	46.42 (46.21)	4.38 (4.21)	9.39 (9.37)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Bu ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (3b)	48.93 (48.80)	4.95 (4.88)	8.72 (8.75)
[Ni(Me ₄ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (3c)	50.91 (50.88)	4.33 (4.27)	8.51 (8.48)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] (4)	73.45 (73.17)	5.05 (4.99)	10.78 (10.67)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (4a)	60.75 (60.69)	4.82 (4.78)	8.54 (8.58)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Bu ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (4b)	62.43 (62.20)	5.41 (5.36)	8.11 (8.06)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (4c)	63.87 (63.82)	4.86 (4.65)	7.89 (7.83)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] (5)	73.84 (73.80)	5.55 (5.46)	10.22 (10.13)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (5a)	61.76 (61.71)	5.22 (5.18)	8.35 (8.22)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Bu ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (5b)	63.21 (63.11)	5.68 (5.71)	7.81 (7.75)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-CH ₃ Bzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (5c)	64.55 (64.64)	5.07 (5.02)	7.55 (7.54)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄)] (6)	64.71 (64.69)	4.11 (4.07)	9.55 (9.43)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Me ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (6a)	54.95 (54.90)	4.07 (4.05)	7.66 (7.76)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Bu ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (6b)	56.65 (56.59)	4.78 (4.62)	7.36 (7.33)
[Ni(Me ₂ Ph ₂ -4-ClBzo ₂ [14]tetraeneN ₄) ₂ .Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (6c)	58.34 (58.21)	3.87 (3.98)	7.11 (7.15)

the formed complex and the cell optical path length is 1 cm. A plot of $C^{\circ}_A C^{\circ}_D / (A - A^{\circ}_A - A^{\circ}_D)$ versus $(C^{\circ}_A + C^{\circ}_D)$ should produce a straight line if only a 1 : 1, and would lead to a curve in a 1 : 2 adduct in a system. For these systems Ketelaar plots have a curvature shape, it indicate that 1 : 2 adducts were formed (Fig. 5).

One series of isosbestic points suggest that there is only one equilibrium system in the adduct formation and the mole ratio curve shows only 2 : 1 complex is formed for all systems (Fig. 6).

Previous studies in our group have shown that nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), manganese(II), iron(II) and cobalt(II) salicylaldehydes are very effective neutral chelating donor ligands for tin(IV)halides²³⁻²⁶. The thermodynamic of interaction of these Schiff base complexes with tin(IV)halides in the solution were investigated. In continuing of those studies, we elucidated steric and electronic effects of a number of nickel macrocycle com-

plexes, and either tin(IV)halides, on the formation constant and thermodynamic parameters of adduct formation. The results show that the interaction between donors and acceptors are related to the type of Schiff base and organo groups on tin(IV)halides.

It is useful to mention that, R₂SnCl₂ compounds are Lewis acids with free coordination sites. Reaction with Lewis bases leads to electronic and steric saturation of Sn center. Numerous complexes of tin(IV) with coordination number higher than four have been characterized²⁷⁻³².

Donor properties of nickel macrocycle complexes :

The formation constants for the nickel complexes with diorganotin(IV)dichlorides were collected in Table 6. On the basis of the results the formation of adducts with one special diorganotin(IV)dichloride follow the sequence below :

Table 6. The formation constants, $\log K_1^a$ and $\log K_2^a$, for nickel macrocycle complexes with diorganotin dichlorides in acetonitrile

Adduct		10 °C	20 °C	30 °C	40 °C
Ph₂SnCl₂					
1	$\log K_1$	3.44 (0.08)	3.32 (0.07)	3.19 (0.10)	3.10 (0.01)
	$\log K_2$	3.55 (0.10)	3.37 (0.01)	3.25 (0.11)	3.16 (0.04)
2	$\log K_1$	3.62 (0.10)	3.37 (0.10)	3.35 (0.10)	3.15 (0.10)
	$\log K_2$	3.69 (0.04)	3.42 (0.03)	3.38 (0.30)	3.22 (0.30)
3	$\log K_1$	2.32 (0.10)	2.25 (0.10)	2.17 (0.10)	2.11 (0.10)
	$\log K_2$	2.47 (0.01)	2.20 (0.02)	2.12 (0.30)	2.08 (0.80)
4	$\log K_1$	2.21 (0.10)	2.14 (0.10)	2.10 (0.10)	1.89 (0.10)
	$\log K_2$	2.29 (0.00)	2.17 (0.00)	2.11 (0.00)	1.98 (0.02)
5	$\log K_1$	2.28 (0.10)	2.18 (0.20)	2.15 (0.21)	2.01 (0.10)
	$\log K_2$	2.42 (0.03)	2.23 (0.03)	2.11 (0.02)	2.07 (0.06)
6	$\log K_1$	2.14 (0.01)	2.10 (0.01)	1.83 (0.01)	1.75 (0.01)
	$\log K_2$	2.20 (0.01)	2.17 (0.01)	2.00 (0.01)	1.88 (0.12)
Me₂SnCl₂					
1	$\log K_1$	2.85 (0.10)	2.70 (0.10)	2.65 (0.10)	2.45 (0.10)
	$\log K_2$	2.86 (0.01)	2.79 (0.05)	2.77 (0.06)	2.59 (0.00)
2	$\log K_1$	3.35 (0.10)	3.29 (0.10)	3.25 (0.10)	3.33 (0.05)
	$\log K_2$	3.40 (0.85)	3.34 (0.17)	3.37 (0.04)	3.41 (0.01)
3	$\log K_1$	2.65 (0.27)	1.85 (0.27)	1.64 (0.04)	1.55 (0.04)
	$\log K_2$	2.25 (0.27)	2.04 (0.30)	1.97 (0.04)	1.93 (0.03)
4	$\log K_1$	1.97 (0.04)	1.53 (0.04)	1.32 (0.04)	1.18 (0.04)
	$\log K_2$	2.14 (0.02)	1.69 (0.01)	1.46 (0.01)	1.29 (0.01)
5	$\log K_1$	2.11 (0.01)	1.67 (0.01)	1.41 (0.01)	1.37 (0.01)
	$\log K_2$	2.17 (0.01)	1.75 (0.20)	1.51 (0.01)	1.40 (0.03)
6	$\log K_1$	1.72 (0.02)	1.38 (0.07)	1.27 (0.09)	1.12 (0.02)
	$\log K_2$	1.90 (0.23)	1.50 (0.44)	1.39 (0.21)	1.15 (0.01)
Bu₂SnCl₂					
1	$\log K_1$	2.47 (0.04)	2.37 (0.04)	2.21 (0.07)	2.18 (0.04)
	$\log K_2$	2.56 (0.00)	2.50 (0.07)	2.36 (0.02)	2.33 (0.00)
2	$\log K_1$	2.84 (0.01)	2.73 (0.01)	2.76 (0.09)	2.64 (0.09)
	$\log K_2$	2.95 (0.10)	2.92 (0.09)	2.87 (0.11)	2.78 (0.10)
3	$\log K_1$	1.99 (0.12)	1.76 (0.23)	1.11 (0.09)	1.00 (0.06)
	$\log K_2$	2.09 (0.03)	1.83 (0.06)	1.33 (0.13)	1.31 (0.11)
4	$\log K_1$	1.73 (0.06)	1.43 (0.06)	0.83 (0.06)	0.63 (0.05)
	$\log K_2$	1.90 (0.10)	1.52 (0.15)	1.02 (0.04)	1.00 (0.20)
5	$\log K_1$	1.88 (0.09)	1.53 (0.03)	1.02 (0.03)	0.88 (0.03)
	$\log K_2$	2.08 (0.16)	1.67 (0.03)	1.15 (0.04)	1.10 (0.02)
6	$\log K_1$	1.51 (0.01)	1.32 (0.01)	0.62 (0.01)	0.51 (0.01)
	$\log K_2$	1.70 (0.01)	1.49 (0.01)	0.59 (0.01)	0.65 (0.01)

^aThe numbers in parentheses are the standard deviations of $\log K$.

> [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)] > [Ni(Me₂Ph₂-4-ClBzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)].

For elucidation of donor properties of nickel

macrocycle complexes, we divided these complexes into two groups : (group 1) [Ni(Me₄-Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₄-4-CH₃Bzo₂[14]tetraeneN₄)], [Ni(Me₄-4-

Fig. 5. Ketellar plot of interaction between $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$ with Me_2SnCl_2 . $P = C^{\circ}_A C^{\circ}_D / (A - A^{\circ}_A - A^{\circ}_D)$ and $C = (C^{\circ}_A + C^{\circ}_D)$.

donor in compare with $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$, and also electron withdrawing groups like chloride (-Cl) reduce the donor property of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-4-ClBzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$, thus the formation constants decrease according to the sequence : $\text{CH}_3 > \text{H} > \text{Cl}$.

The acceptor properties of diorganotin(IV)dichlorides :

Comparing the formation constant values for interac-

Fig. 6. Mole ratio plot for titration of $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$ with Ph_2SnCl_2 at 390 nm, 2 : 1 adduct.

$\text{ClBzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4]$ and (group 2) $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-4-CH}_3\text{Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-4-ClBzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$ and then investigated results in two parts.

Comparing the donor property of nickel complexes between two groups :

In this section we compare (for example) $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$ from group 1 and $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{-Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$ from group 2, the results shown that existing of phenyl rings as electron withdrawing groups on complexes of group 2 decrease the donor ability of nickel complexes of group 2, it is clear from reducing of the formation constants. This result was noticed for other couple complexes between two groups.

Comparing the donor property of nickel complexes in one group :

In a selected group, for example group 1; existing of methyl (-CH₃) groups as electron realizing groups make $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{-4-CH}_3\text{Bzo}_2[14]\text{-tetraeneN}_4)]$ complex as a better

tion between one nickel complex and three diorganotin(IV)dichlorides, the following trend of acidity for the Lewis acids used was assessed : $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 > \text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2 > \text{Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$.

It is clear that the electron withdrawing groups (Ph-) on the tin center makes Ph_2SnCl_2 a stronger Lewis acid than the others. This trend also indicate that replacing the methyl- by a more bulky butyl- group on an organotin(IV) compound causes a weakening of the interactions. The butyl- group can affect the interaction in two ways : (i) a more bulky butyl- group makes adduct formation unfavorable because of its greater steric hindrance than a methyl- group³³. (ii) butyl- groups, though, have better electron releasing properties to reduce the acid strength of an organotin(IV) Lewis acid and to decrease its interaction with nickel complexes as donors.

Conclusion

By considering the formation constants and the ΔG° of the adduct formation for Ni^{II} macrocycle complexes as donor and the diorganotin(IV)dichlorides as acceptor, the

following conclusions have been drawn :

(i) The formation constant for a given donor change according to the following trend for Ni^{II} macrocycle complexes due to the electronic effects :

(ii) The formation constant for a given R₂SnCl₂ acceptor toward the nickel macrocycle complex change according to the following trend :

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